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The Future Of Finance: The Impact Of AI-Powered Robotic Process Automation On The Efficiency Of Commercial Bank In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the Impact of AI-powered robotic process automation on the efficiency of commercial Bank in Anambra state. The study developed three objectives such as to; examine the effect of AI-powered RPA on operational efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State, assess the influence of AI-powered RPA on transaction processing speed in commercial banks in Anambra State; assess the influence of AI-powered RPA on customer service efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State. This research work will be anchored on the Theory of Task-Technology Fit (TTF). The study adopted survey research design. Data were generated from primary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the selected commercial bank in Anambra state. The population of the study was 4,629 staff. The sample size of the study was eight hundred and ninety (890) which was gotten through Borg & Gall (1973) formular, While eight hundred and seventy-one (871) were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using correlation analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that AI-powered RPA has significant effect on operational efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State; AI-powered RPA has significant effect on transaction processing speed in commercial banks in Anambra State; AI-powered RPA has significant effect on customer service efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State. The study concludes that AI-powered RPA is a critical technological tool for enhancing efficiency and competitiveness in the Nigerian banking sector, particularly within Anambra State. The study recommends that; Commercial banks in Anambra State should intensify the adoption and deployment of AI-powered RPA across core banking operations such as transaction processing, customer on boarding, compliance monitoring, and report generation to improve efficiency. Banks should invest in continuous training programs to equip employees with the necessary skills to work effectively with AI-powered RPA systems. This will ensure smooth human-machine collaboration and reduce resistance to technological change.

Keywords: AI-powered RPA, operational efficiency, transaction processing speed, customer service efficiency

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly evolving financial landscape, technological innovation has become a key driver of competitive advantage and operational effectiveness. Among the transformative technologies reshaping the banking sector, Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered Robotic Process Automation (RPA) stands out for its potential to significantly enhance operational efficiency, reduce costs, and improve service delivery.

RPA refers to software robots or “bots” that mimic human actions to automate repetitive, rule-based tasks (Adejuwon, & Unuesiri, 2024). When integrated with AI capabilities such as machine learning, natural language processing, and decision-making algorithms RPA evolves into a more intelligent system capable of handling complex processes that were traditionally dependent on human cognitive abilities (Bataev, & Davydov, 2020).

Commercial banks operate in a highly dynamic environment characterized by increasing customer expectations, stringent regulatory requirements, and the need for rapid, error-free transaction processing (Chinedu-Chiejine & Owa, 2023). In this context, enhancing efficiency is not only a strategic priority but also a necessity for survival and growth. In Anambra State, Nigeria, commercial banks play a critical role in facilitating economic activities, providing financial services to individuals, businesses, and government entities. However, these banks face challenges related to manual processing, human error, high operational costs, and prolonged turnaround times all of which hinder service quality and operational effectiveness (Ezeamama Orji, and Obani, 2024)..

The adoption of AI-powered RPA offers a strategic solution to these challenges by automating routine processes such as account opening, loan processing, transaction reconciliation, compliance reporting, and customer inquiry handling (Ezeamama, 2019). By reducing dependence on manual labor and enhancing the accuracy and speed of operations, AI-driven automation can significantly improve workflow efficiency and allow bank personnel to focus on higher-value tasks that demand human judgment and creativity (Ezeamama & Obani, 2024).

Despite the theoretical benefits of AI-powered RPA, empirical evidence on its practical impact especially within the context of commercial banks in Anambra State remains limited. Understanding how these technologies influence operational performance, customer satisfaction, and overall organizational effectiveness is essential for bank executives, policymakers, and stakeholders aiming to make informed decisions about technology investments (Ezeamama & Orji, 2024)..

Therefore, this study seeks to examine the impact of AI-powered Robotic Process Automation on the efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State, exploring both the tangible benefits and the obstacles associated with technology adoption. By doing so, the research will contribute to the broader discourse on digital transformation in the banking sector and offer insights that could guide future implementations of intelligent automation in Nigeria’s financial services industry.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to examine the impact of AI-powered Robotic Process Automation on the efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State.

Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. examine the effect of AI-powered RPA on operational efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State;
- ii. assess the influence of AI-powered RPA on transaction processing speed in commercial banks in Anambra State;
- iii. assess the influence of AI-powered RPA on customer service efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 AI-Powered Robotic Process Automation (RPA)

AI-powered Robotic Process Automation (RPA) refers to the integration of artificial intelligence technologies with traditional robotic process automation to enable software robots (bots) to perform complex, intelligent, and adaptive business processes with minimal human intervention. Unlike conventional RPA, which is limited to rule-based and structured tasks, AI-powered RPA incorporates capabilities such as machine learning, natural language processing, computer vision, and predictive analytics to handle unstructured data, make decisions, and learn from experience (Dahlia & Aini, 2021).

In the banking sector, AI-powered RPA automates repetitive and time-consuming processes such as transaction processing, customer onboarding, account reconciliation, loan processing, fraud detection, compliance reporting, and customer service interactions (Doguc, 2020). By mimicking human actions across multiple digital systems, AI-powered RPA improves processing speed, accuracy, and consistency while reducing operational errors and costs. AI-powered RPA also enables continuous process improvement, as intelligent bots can analyze large volumes of data, identify patterns, and adapt workflows based on changing business rules or customer behavior (Durão, & dos Reis, 2024). This capability allows banks to respond more quickly to market demands, regulatory changes, and customer expectations. AI-powered Robotic Process Automation represents a strategic digital transformation tool that enhances operational efficiency, employee productivity, service quality, and competitive advantage in commercial banks. Its adoption supports innovation, scalability, and sustainability in modern banking operations, particularly in emerging economies such as Nigeria (E-Fatima, Khandan, Hosseinian-Far, & Sarwar, 2023).

2.1.2 Efficiency

Efficiency comprises the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended outputs (or goals and objectives). According to Richard *et al.* (2019), organizational efficiency three specific areas of firm outcomes: financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment, etc.); product market performance (sales, market share, etc.); and shareholder return (total shareholder return, economic value added, etc). Organizational efficiency is the ultimate dependent variable of interest for researchers concerned with just about any area of management (Devinney *et al.*, 2010). This broad construct is essential in allowing researchers and managers to evaluate firms over time and compare them to rivals. In short organizational efficiency is the most important criterion in evaluating organizations, their actions, and environments.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Theory of Task-Technology Fit (TTF).

This theory of TTF was propounded by Googhue and Thompson in 1995, to explain the utilization of technology to intended users on the anticipated tasks' requirements in other words; it advocates a means of quantifying the effectiveness of technology in a structured system, by assessing the relationship between the robotics and the tasks the technology aims to support (Spies, Grobbelaar, & Botha). The aim of TTF theory was to add to the body of knowledge on technology implementation as well as usage of various technologies in a system. This theory appears to be widely recognized and often use to justify the application of technology in a system especially in the aspect of literature. Therefore, this theory relates to robotic process automated accounting and finance services in the Nigerian listed firms.

This study therefore is hinge on TTF theory since it appears to have better theoretical disposition which explains and supports RPAAFs in aspect and extent to which robotic processes automation add value to organizational systems when the system eventually harness the organizations tasks and the proposed accounting and finance technologies which is usually structured alongside with the organizations business activities (Systems processes). This compatibility would determine the effect on the performance and how robotic process automation system would be improve accounting and finance services. Mamudu and Lamido (2017), noted that industrial robots adoption and implementation poses potentially as a new highly paying jobs.

2.3 Empirical Review

Abdalla (2025) examine the impact of artificial intelligence through robotic process automation systems on internal audit operation efficiency in Jordanian commercial banks. The study uses a descriptive methodology to evaluate how robotic process automation systems enhance the different dimensions of internal audit efficiency: planning, management, execution, and communication. The study designed a structured questionnaire for data collection. The sample consisted of 12 commercial bank employees whose working processes are directly affected by robotic process automation system procedures which puts them in a unique position to comment on the practical applicability of this technology and its

implications for internal audit. In this study, 480 electronic questionnaires were distributed via Google Forms, and 390 completed forms were collected for further analysis. The study employs descriptive statistics and advanced statistical techniques, such as linear regression analysis, for data analysis. The findings indicate that robotic process automation systems enhance the internal audit process by reducing the cost of operations, eliminating human errors, and smoothing work processes. The robotic process automation system will allow continuous auditing, real-time risk management, and proper reporting; hence, it will change the role of internal auditors and, in the end, improve organizational compliance and performance. This study asserts that the banking industry must integrate AI-driven automation to maintain its competitiveness in the constantly changing financial landscape.

Mohammed (2025) explores AI's impact on commercial banks in Oman, focusing on its role in digital transformation, automation, fraud detection, and personalized services. Through a combination of qualitative and quantitative analysis, the research examines how AI-driven technologies like chatbots, machine learning, and predictive analytics optimize banking operations and customer satisfaction. The study also addresses challenges such as cyber security risks, regulatory compliance, and workforce adaptation. Findings reveal that AI contributes to cost reduction, increased efficiency, and a competitive edge, while emphasizing the importance of a balanced approach to its integration. The research offers recommendations for maximizing AI adoption in Omani banks to foster sustainable growth and innovation.

Adejuwon, and Unuesiri (2024) investigated the effect of Robotics and Natural Language Processing (NLP) on the Financial Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The study analysed secondary data of selected DMBs for the period 2015 -2023 (9 years). The data were sourced from the Annual Reports of the DMBs, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin and World Development Indicators to establish cause-effect relationships between the variables. The population of the study was the 27 DMBs in Nigeria as at 31st July, 2023, while the sample size was five (5) DMBs (Access Bank, Zenith Bank, UBA, First Bank and GT Bank)The sampling technique used was the non-probability convenience sampling method chosen based on the availability of the financial statements of the DMBs for the period under study. The study employed Error Correction Model (ECM) for time series regression to analyse equilibrium relationships in short run and long run behaviours. The hypothesis was used to test the impact of deployment of robotics on the financial performance of DMBs in Nigeria. The resultant coefficients were positive, but not significant both during pre-and post-Robotics adoption (coefficient = 0.49718, p)

Ogiriki, and Marcus, (2025) explored the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and its influence on corporate governance effectiveness' in Nigerian commercial banks, with a focus on decision quality. In the modern digital banking landscape, AI technologies including fraud detection systems, automated risk assessments, and data analytics play a crucial role in enhancing transparency, internal controls, and risk management. Guided by Agency Theory, the study demonstrates how AI reduces information asymmetry, strengthens oversight, and aligns managerial actions with the interests of stakeholders. Despite its benefits in improving efficiency and decision-making accuracy, challenges such as data privacy concerns, algorithmic bias, and employee resistance remain. The study recommends robust governance frameworks, staff capacity building, and regulatory compliance measures to maximize the potential of AI as a transformative tool for enhancing corporate governance and driving sustainable performance in Nigeria's banking sector.

Chibole, and Ondara (2025) examined the impact of AI technologies on process efficiency in selected commercial banks in Kenya. The study applied the technology acceptance model, resource-based view model, and the diffusion of innovation theory. The four independent variables: machine learning, robotic process automation, natural language processing, and predictive analytics, were analyzed in relation to process efficiency. The target population comprised of the 38 commercial banks in Kenya. The sampling frame was Equity Bank, Kenya Commercial Bank (KCB), Cooperative Bank, NCBA Bank, and Standard Chartered Bank branches in Nairobi County. The unit of analysis included the banks' branch managers and information technology managers, who were selected via purposive sampling. The sample size was

192 participants. Data was collected via closed-ended questionnaires, with a pilot study involving 19 participants to inform the questionnaire's reliability and validity pre-tests. SPSS version 22 was used for statistical analysis, and the findings presented in tables and charts. The researcher complied with appropriate ethical protocols. The findings showed that machine learning, robotic process automation, natural language processing, and predictive analytics impacted process efficiency in various magnitudes. All the four regression coefficients were statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. Robotic process automation had the most significant impact on process efficiency while predictive analytics had the least impact. The results of the correlation analysis showed a positive, strong and significant relationship between each of the four independent variables and process efficiency.

Oyenyi, Ugochukwu, and Mhlongo, (2024) examined the impacts of AI integration within this sector. Anchored in a robust thematic analysis and an exhaustive literature review, the study meticulously navigates through the evolution, current applications and prospective future of AI in banking, with a particular focus on enhancing customer experience and addressing the operational challenges. The methodology adopted herein, comprising both qualitative and quantitative analyses, facilitates a comprehensive exploration of AI's role in banking, unveiling its potential to revolutionize service delivery, risk management and customer engagement. The findings from this investigation underscore the significant enhancements in customer service metrics attributed to AI, alongside the emergence of personalized banking experiences. Furthermore, the study illuminates the strategic implications for banks adopting AI technologies, highlighting the necessity of navigating ethical and privacy concerns meticulously. The conclusions drawn advocate for a balanced approach towards AI adoption, emphasizing the imperative of ongoing research and development, coupled with ethical considerations, to harness AI's full potential responsibly. In essence, this paper offers a scholarly synthesis of AI's transformative impact on banking, providing a roadmap for future explorations in this domain. It lays down the gauntlet for banks to leverage AI's potential judiciously, guiding the banking sector towards a future where technology and human ingenuity converge to redefine banking's essence.

METHODOLOGY

3.1: Research Design

The study adopted descriptive survey design to assess the the impact of AI-powered Robotic Process Automation on the efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State. Survey research design was chosen because the sampled elements and the variables that are being studied are simply being observed as they are without making any attempt to control or manipulate them. The primary source of data was used in this study because of the variables that were used. Questionnaire and semi-structured interview were used to collect data from the bank staff

3.2: Population of the Study.

This describes number of staff in selected deposit money bank in, Anambra, which constitutes the universe of this study. The population of interest therefore consisted of all workers in deposit money banks in Anambra State. However six commercial banks with international authorization operating in the state were selected for the study by the use of purposive sampling. Thus, the study population for this research comprises of employees of the selected commercial banks in Anambra State, Nigeria.

s/n	Bank	Population	Nnewi	Onitsha	Awka	Total
1	Fidelity bank	423	3	10	3	16
2	First bank	765	2	11	6	19
3	Access bank	1,332	3	12	5	20
4	Union bank	514	1	3	2	6
5	GT bank	823	1	4	2	7
6	UBA	772	3	10	6	19
	Total	4,629				

Sources: Human sources of selected banks

3.3: Determination of Sample Size

The sample size for this study will be determined by using the Borg & Gall formular of (1973). Statistically, the Borg & Gall (1973) formular for sample size is given by

$$n = (Z_x)^2(e) [N]$$

$$(Z_x)^2 = 1.960$$

e = Error margin (0.05)

N = Population of Interest =

X = Significance Level

3.4 Sample Size Determination

Given the nature of this study, it was difficult to cover the entire population of (4,629), so a fair representative sample of the population therefore was imperative. Accordingly, the sample size for the study was determined by using the Borg & Gall (1973) formular for calculating sample size as follows

$$n = (1.960)^2 (0.05) [4629]$$

$$n = (1.960)^2 (0.05) [4629]$$

$$n = (3.8461) (231.45)$$

$$= 890.171945 \implies 890$$

$$n = 890$$

Thereafter, convenience sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents from each of the sample deposit money banks. The essence is to give all respondents equal chance of been selected for the study. Only the employees of the deposit money banks will be the sample for the study.

The researcher adopted the use of questionnaire as a method of data collection instrument to the identified set of respondents. Questionnaire is an instrument used to gather data, which allows measurement for or against a particular viewpoint.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

4.1 Distributions of Questionnaire

Table 4.1.1 Information on Distribution of Questionnaire

s/n	Options	No of Respondents	Percentage %
1	Questionnaire Distributed	890	100%
2	Questionnaire Returned	889	99%
3	Questionnaire Completed	871	97%
4	Questionnaire Not Duly Completed	10	1%
5	Questionnaire Missing	8	0.8%

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 4.1 showed that a total number of eight hundred and ninety (890) copies of questionnaire were distributed to the respondents, eight hundred and eighty-nine (889) copies which represented 99% were returned, eight hundred, seventy-one (871) which represent 97% where completed and ten (10) copies which represented 1% were not duly completed by the respondents, while eight (8) copies which represented only 0.8% of the total questionnaire were missing. Hence, the analyses for this study were based on the eight hundred and seventy-one (871) copies which represented 97% of the sample population.

4.2 Test of Statement of Hypotheses

Ho₁: AI-powered RPA has no significant effect on operational efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State;

Ho₂: AI-powered RPA has no significant effect on transaction processing speed in commercial banks in Anambra State;

Ho₃: AI-powered RPA has no significant effect on customer service efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State.

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: AI-powered RPA has no significant effect on operational efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State;

4.3.3 Correlation Analysis Test

Table 4.1.2: Relationship between AI-powered RPA and Operational Efficiency

	AI-powered RPA	Operational efficiency
AI-powered RPA	1	** .743
Pearson Correlation		.000
Sig. (2-tailed)	.871	.871
N		
Operational efficiency	.743	1
Pearson Correlation	.000	
Sig. (2-tailed)	.871	.871
N		

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Vision 23.0

Table 4.1.2 indicates that the $r = .743$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ which is less than 0.05, ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, reject H₀ and accept H₁. Hence, AI-powered RPA positively correlated with Operational Efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State;. From the result, Correlation is 0.743, 74.3% shows that there is positive relationship between AI-powered RPA and Operational Efficiency because of the positive value for correlation coefficient. Thus, when increasing in AI-powered RPA, Operational Efficiency will be getting higher. The value of this correlation coefficient 0.74.3 is fall under coefficient range from + 0.70 to + 0.80. Therefore, the relationship between AI-powered RPA and Operational Efficiency is high.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₁: AI-powered RPA has no significant effect on transaction processing speed of commercial banks in Anambra State

Table 4.1.3: Relationship between AI-powered RPA and transaction processing speed

	AI-powered RPA	Transaction processing speed
AI-powered RPA	1	.090
Pearson Correlation		.000
Sig. (2-tailed)	.871	.871
N		
Transaction processing speed	.090	1
Pearson Correlation	.000	
Sig. (2-tailed)	.587	.587
N		

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Vision 23.0

According to the analysis, $r = .090$, $p\text{-value}$ is 0.000 which is less than the significant level of 0.05, ($p > 0.05$). Therefore, Ho reject and accept H₁. Therefore we can state that there is a significant positive relationship between AI-powered RPA and transaction processing speed of commercial banks in Anambra State. From the result, the Pearson Correlation (R-value) between Ai-powered PRA and transaction processing speed is 0.90, 90%. This means there is a positive AI-powered RPA variables. Whereby, the increase in AI-Power PRA will lead to increase in transaction processing speed of commercial banks in Anambra state. The value of this correlation coefficient 0.90 is fall under coefficient

range from + 0.71 to + 0.90. Therefore, the relationship between Ai-Powered PRA and transaction processing speed is high

Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: AI-powered RPA has no significant effect on customer service efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State

Table 4.1.4: Relationship between AI-powered RPA and customer service efficiency

	AI-powered RPA	customer service efficiency
AI-powered RPA	1	.083**
Pearson Correlation		.000
Sig. (2-tailed)	587	587
N		
Customer Service Efficiency	.083	1
Pearson Correlation	.000	587
Sig. (2-tailed)	587	
N		

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Vision 23.0

Table 4.1.4 shows that the $r = .083$, p-value is 0.000 which is less than the significant level of 0.01, ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, H₀ will be rejected and H₁ is accepted therefore, AI-powered RPA positively relate to customer service efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State, Nigeria. Based on the result, the Pearson Correlation (R-value) is 0.838, 83.8%; this indicates that there is a positive value between AI-powered RPA and customer service efficiency. In the other words, when AI-powered RPA is increasing, customer service efficiency will increase simultaneously. The value of this correlation coefficient 0.83.8 is fall under coefficient range from + 0.71 to + 0.80. Therefore, the relationship between AI-powered RPA and customer service efficiency is high.

4.3 DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The study found that AI-powered RPA has significant positive effect on efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra state. The findings imply that bank management should prioritize the adoption and expansion of intelligent automation systems. By automating repetitive and rule-based processes such as account opening, transaction processing, compliance reporting, and customer on boarding, management can reduce processing time, minimize human errors, and improve service delivery. This finding suggests that managerial focus should shift toward strategic oversight rather than routine operational tasks. The result indicates that AI-powered RPA enhances speed, accuracy, and consistency in banking operations. Commercial banks in Anambra State can leverage RPA to streamline workflows, reduce delays in service execution, and ensure uninterrupted operations. This implies that banks adopting RPA are better positioned to handle high transaction volumes efficiently, especially during peak banking periods. The significant effect on efficiency implies improved customer experience in commercial banks. Faster transaction processing, reduced waiting time, and fewer service errors enhance customer satisfaction and trust. This suggests that banks implementing AI-powered RPA can gain competitive advantage through superior service quality. The findings are in line with the study of Abdalla (2025), Mohammed (2025) Adejuwon, & Unuesiri , (2024), Ogiriki, & Marcus, (2025) Chibole, & Ondara, (2025).

5.1 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study examined the effect of AI-powered Robotic Process Automation on the efficiency of commercial banks in Anambra State. The findings revealed that AI-powered RPA has a significant positive effect on operational efficiency, indicating that banks that adopt intelligent automation

experience faster service delivery, improved accuracy, reduced operational costs, and enhanced productivity. The integration of AI-driven RPA enables banks to automate repetitive and routine processes, thereby minimizing human error and improving consistency in service execution. Overall, the study concludes that AI-powered RPA is a critical technological tool for enhancing efficiency and competitiveness in the Nigerian banking sector, particularly within Anambra State. The study recommend that Commercial banks in Anambra State should intensify the adoption and deployment of AI-powered RPA across core banking operations such as transaction processing, customer on boarding, compliance monitoring, and report generation to improve efficiency. Banks should invest in continuous training programs to equip employees with the necessary skills to work effectively with AI-powered RPA systems. This will ensure smooth human-machine collaboration and reduce resistance to technological change. Banks should upgrade their IT infrastructure and enhance cybersecurity measures to support the effective functioning of AI-powered RPA systems and protect sensitive customer data.

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